

formamide and dioxane. The hydrated complexes lose associated water molecules below 120°. The loss of water molecules at low temperature indicates that they are uncoordinated. The failure of these compounds to form pyridine or picoline adducts further support the uncoordinated nature of water molecules.

The oxomolybdenum(v) complexes are diamagnetic (Table 1) similar to dinuclear μ -oxomolybdenum(v) complexes⁴. Vanadyl complexes show normal magnetic moment values indicating absence of exchange interaction in the complexes. Oxomolybdenum(v) complexes are dark brown or brickred in colour and do not display well resolved absorption bands in the visible region. In some complexes two or three broad and weak absorption bands are observed in the regions 22 500–24 500, 19 500–21 800 and 13 800–15 200 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3E(II)$, ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3B_1$ and ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^3E(I)$ transitions respectively in distorted octahedral field⁵. Oxovanadium(IV) complex $[\text{VO}(\text{tcH})\text{SO}_4]$ displays a shoulder at 17 280 and a medium band at 19 600 cm^{-1} assignable to $b_2 \rightarrow a_1^*$ and $b_2 \rightarrow e_g^*$ transitions⁶. The complexes $[\text{VO}L_2] \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ display ligand field transitions at 21 000 and 17 580 cm^{-1} as broad and weak bands.

The infrared spectra of tcH displays NH stretch at 3 280 and 3 200 cm^{-1} which shifted to lower frequency by 30–50 cm^{-1} on complexation indicating coordination of NH_2 nitrogen. The NH stretches of thiocarbohydrazones located near 3 150–3 320 cm^{-1} are observed as broad band due to mixing of OH stretch of water molecules and NH stretches of NH and NH_2 groups in the complexes. The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ of ligands are obtained at 850–880 cm^{-1} which shifted to lower frequency in the complexes by 50–80 cm^{-1} indicating the coordination of thioamide sulphur with metal atom. The δ_{NH_2} of thiocarbohydrazone observed at $1\,610 \pm 10$ cm^{-1} is not affected appreciable in the complexes indicating that the terminal NH_2 nitrogen is not involved in coordination.

The nature and position of Mo=O stretch has been taken as diagnostic of monomeric and dimeric μ -oxo complexes of oxomolybdenum(v). The oxomolybdenum(v) complexes display a broad and very strong band at 950–970 cm^{-1} . The

$\nu(\text{Mo} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array} \text{Mo})$ band has been found at 810–850 cm^{-1} supporting the oxo-bridging in the complexes. In the vanadyl complexes $\nu_{\text{V=O}}$ is seen at 970–930 cm^{-1} (the normal range of V=O group) indicates that V=O oxygen is not involved in dimerisation or polymerisation⁷.

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Complexes of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with *N*-Acetyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide

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TRANSITION metal complexes of sulphur donor ligand are finding extensive uses¹. The present paper reports the preparation and study the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *N*-acetyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide (APTC).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. *N*-Acetyl-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide was prepared following the reported procedure². An alcoholic solution of the metal salt was added to a solution of the ligand in acetone with 1 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting mixture was stirred vigorously when a coloured compound precipitated which was filtered, washed with alcohol followed by acetone and dried under reduced pressure. Attempts to prepare the perchlorate complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} and the bromo complex of Ni^{II} were unsuccessful. The complexes were found to be highly insoluble in water but sparingly soluble in common organic solvents.

The analytical³ and physical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The magnetic susceptibility were measured at room temperature

by Guoy method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-12 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a CL-54 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The low conductance values of all the complexes (6.00–8.70 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) suggest their non-electrolytic nature. All the complexes were found to possess low magnetic moment which may be due to spin-spin interaction. The molecular weight (Rast's camphor method) values of the complexes indicate the dimeric nature of the complexes.

The ir spectra of ligand show a broad band at 3 320–3 000 cm^{-1} which represents a series of overlapping stretching vibrations corresponding to NH groups. The CH stretch of aromatic ring (3 100–3 000 cm^{-1}) seems to have been enveloped by the NH stretching vibrations. In all the metal complexes other than copper, two to three bands with reduced intensity appear at 3 320s, 3 260m and 3 120w cm^{-1} . Coordination of metal through nitrogen should cause splitting of these bands and decrease in intensities. The bands at 3 260 and 3 120 cm^{-1} may be due to the splitting of the NH stretching vibration⁴. The band at 3 320s cm^{-1} may be due to NH stretching vibration similar to amide group. In the region 1 700–1 340 cm^{-1} , the ligand as well as the metal complexes show three to four bands. Some of the bands are due to phenyl ring vibration. The band appearing at $\sim 1 670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to C=O stretching vibration⁵ due to its intensity and sharpness. It shifts to a lower frequency region by 60–70 cm^{-1} in all the metal complexes. A strong band observed at 1 500 cm^{-1} seems to be due to C–N vibration⁶ of the ligand. It undergoes a blue-shift in the metal complexes and appears at 1 560 cm^{-1} indicating the increasing double bond character of NCN

vibration. Two medium to strong bands appear at 1 590 and 1 340 cm^{-1} , the first band may be due to C=C vibrations of phenyl ring and the latter due to overlapping stretching vibration of N–C–N and C=S. The band appearing at 1 215 cm^{-1} (C=S)⁷ in the ligand shifts to lower frequency region (1 165 cm^{-1}) in all the metal complexes. It indicates clearly the coordination of sulphur atom with the metal ions. Three bands observed in the ligand at 1 270, 1 240 and 1 140 cm^{-1} . Some of these bands are also found in the metal complexes with minor vibration in their positions. This may be attributed to substituted phenyl ring⁸. Two other band at 750 and 720 cm^{-1} of the ligand shift in an irregular way in the metal complexes. These bands probably arise due to out-of-plane CH bending absorptions due to the substituted aromatic ring⁹. Additional bands appear in the nitrate complex at 1 520, 1 300 and 930 cm^{-1} which can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{N-O}}$ of the coordinated NO_3 group. The perchlorate complexes show three significant bands at 1 260w, 1 100s and 980w cm^{-1} which can be assigned ν_3 , ν_2 and ν_1 vibrations, respectively¹⁰. The above ir spectral data suggest that the ligand is coordinated to the metal ion through N, S and O atoms.

The electronic spectra of the ligand reveal bands near 31 250 (ϵ 24 340), 41 600 (41 600) and 49 000 cm^{-1} (49 500) which may be assigned to either $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ or $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The Cu^{II} complexes show magnetic moments in the range 1.70–1.90 B. M. The low value may be either due to the spin-spin interaction of Cu^{II} ions or partial reduction of Cu^{II} to Cu^{I} state during the synthesis of the complex¹¹. The oxidation state of copper was tested volumetrically to be +2. This suggests that the low values may be due to spin-spin interaction of the Cu^{II} ions resulting partial quenching of paramagnetism. The electronic spectra of these

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Mol. wt. Found/ (Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				# _{eff} B.M.
			M	S	N	Cl/Br	
APTC	Yellow	—	—	16.1 (16.5)	14.0 (14.4)	—	—
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{APTC})_2\text{Cl}_4$	Pale blue	645.0 (657.0)	19.0 (19.3)	9.4 (9.7)	8.1 (8.5)	21.2 (21.6)	1.70
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{APTC})_2\text{Br}_4$	White	828.0 (835.0)	14.9 (15.2)	7.3 (7.7)	6.1 (6.7)	37.8 (38.8)	1.74
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{APTC})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4$	Brownish yellow	751.0 (763.0)	16.2 (16.7)	8.0 (8.4)	14.1 (14.6)	—	1.80
$\text{Cu}_2(\text{APTC})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_4$	Pea green	889.0 (918.0)	13.4 (13.9)	6.8 (7.0)	5.9 (6.1)	15.1 (15.6)	1.9
$\text{Ni}_2(\text{APTC})_2\text{Cl}_4$	Yellowish white	639.0 (649.0)	18.6 (18.8)	10.2 (9.9)	8.9 (8.6)	22.1 (21.9)	2.81
$\text{Ni}_2(\text{APTC})_2\text{Br}_4$	Pink	816.0 (827)	14.0 (14.4)	7.1 (7.7)	6.3 (6.8)	38.8 (38.7)	3.0
$\text{Co}_2(\text{APTC})_2\text{Cl}_4$	Brown	638 (650)	17.9 (18.4)	9.5 (9.9)	8.1 (8.6)	21.4 (21.9)	4.20
$\text{Co}_2(\text{APTC})_2\text{Br}_4$	Pale yellow	817 (828)	13.9 (14.5)	7.2 (7.7)	6.5 (6.8)	38.1 (38.7)	4.84
$\text{Co}_2(\text{APTC})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4$	Pale brown	750 (756)	15.9 (15.9)	8.4 (8.5)	14.6 (14.8)	—	4.7

complexes show one or two broad band(s) in the region 14 000–18 800 cm^{-1} and charge transfer band near 25 000 cm^{-1} . Cu^{II} carboxylates which are diamagnetic, show three bands¹² at 11 000, 13 500 and 26 000 cm^{-1} . Another diamagnetic Cu^{II} complex with diazoaminobenzene¹³ shows two bands at 14 900 and 18 800 cm^{-1} which are assigned to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$, respectively. All the Cu^{II} complexes in which the paramagnetism is partially or fully quenched absorb¹⁴ around 26 600 cm^{-1} . The spectra of the present complexes show both ligand and charge transfer bands like the spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes with diazoaminobenzene. The visible absorption spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show broad asymmetric bands at 10 600, 12 000, 15 000 and 18 000 cm^{-1} followed by a strong band at 27 000 cm^{-1} . In an octahedral approximation¹⁵ the first two bands can be assigned to the split components of ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, i.e. ${}^3B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ and the next two due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) \nu_g$, i.e. ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. The high frequency band corresponds to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) \nu_g$ transition. The complexes exhibit low magnetic moments¹⁶ (2.81–3.0 B.M.) which may be due to partial quenching of paramagnetism because of spin-spin interaction. The Co^{II} complexes shows bands at 16 000–20 000 cm^{-1} which are similar to the electronic spectra of known octahedral complexes^{15,17}. The spectral transitions may arise due to ligand field transition of octahedral compounds of the Co^{II} complex and may be assigned to ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transition. Besides, the charge transfer band appears at 27 000 cm^{-1} . The lower magnetic moments (4.2–4.7 B.M.) of these complexes may arise either due to electron pairing for a strong covalent bond involving the 3d-electron of Co^{II} ions or spin-spin interaction.

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Interaction of Alkaline Earth Metals with Aspirin

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KINETIC parameters, viz. transfer coefficient (α), standard rate constant (k_a^0)_B of the overall reaction, standard potential (E^0)_B of the overall reaction and

$$k_a^* = (k_a^0)_B \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{D_{Mx}}} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{D}} \right)^\alpha C^{-(1-\alpha)+1} \quad (1)$$

provide evidence for quasi-reversible reduction nature of aspirin in NH_4ClO_4 at pH 4.8 in contrast with the established irreversible nature¹. The stability constant (K) of the metal ions with aspirin revealed strong complexation in the order, $\text{Ba}^{2+} < \text{Sr}^{2+} < \text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+}$. Thermodynamic functions² have been calculated to explain equilibrium condition during complexation.

Experimental

The ionic strength $\mu=0.5$ was maintained by NH_4ClO_4 . pH of the solution was adjusted at 4.8 by adding requisite amounts of HClO_4 and NH_4OH . Concentration of metal ions was kept constant at $5 \times 10^{-5} M$. Sodium alkyl sulphate, tetradecyl (C_{14}), hexadecyl (C_{16}) and octadecyl (C_{18}) (Procter and Gamble) were pure white crystalline compounds and used as such.

An universal polarograph OH-105 (Radelkis, Hungary) was used to record polarograms. DME had the capillary characteristics $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.66 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$ in open circuit at $h=47 \text{ cm}$. In order to maintain precision, graphically obtained i_a and $E_{1/2}$ values were simultaneously refined by applying least-square based computer programme^{3,6}. Solutions were deoxygenated by bubbling prepurified nitrogen prior to recording C–V curves. All potentials refer to SCE. Triton X-100 (0.005%) was added to eliminate maxima and hydrolysis of aspirin. Temperatures of 25 ± 0.02 , 35 ± 0.02 and $45 \pm 0.02^\circ$ were maintained by an Ultrathermostat NBE (G.D.R.). Most of the experimental data have been obtained at $25 \pm 0.02^\circ$.